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TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN

Muxammadiyev Maxmud

FOR PUBLICATION OF PAPER ENTITLED
THEME: RAQAMLI PLATFORMALAR MODELI VA ULARNING
MIKROIQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGI

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DATE

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